

OpenSky for Aircraft Track Validation: Data

The data generated by the verification tool contains time-delta information about each flight track observed by at least two OpenSky sensors.

For every observed flight track, the ICAO identifier is stored. For each pair of sensors, which observed some common subset of messages from this flight track, their OpenSky sensor ids are stored, along with three values for each message received by both sensors:

- The measured time-delta (based on the unsynchronized sensor clocks)
- The expected time-delta (based on the advertised location of the message and the sensors)
- The server timestamp, when the message was first received by the OpenSky server

These three values are all stored in units of nanoseconds.

Thus, an output file may look as follows:

```
[
  ["ABC123", // ICAO aircraft identifier
    [
      [123, 456], // IDs of two sensors which observed a common subset of
      messages
      [
        [1000, 150, 167XXXXXXXXXXXXXXX], // measured time-delta,
        expected time-delta, and server-timestamp
        [1010, 155, 167XXXXXXXXXXXXXXX],
        [990, 148, 167XXXXXXXXXXXXXXX],
      ]
    ],
    [
      [123, 789], // Second pair of sensors which observed some messages
      [...] // list of three-tuples (measured and expected time-delta,
      server-timestamp)
    ]
  ], // end of information for flight track of aircraft ABC123
  ["DEF456", // information about next aircraft
    [...],
  ]
]
```

Check the analysis.ipynb for examples of how to parse and visualize this data.